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Federated Learning for Time-Series Clustering in
Healthcare: A Privacy-Preserving Framework for Patient
Risk Analysis Improvement

by

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Abstract

The rapid growth of chronic diseases such as diabetes has created an urgent need for advanced methods to analyse healthcare data while respecting strict privacy regulations. Traditional machine learning approaches are limited in this context because they require centralised data sharing, which is often restricted by frameworks such as GDPR and HIPAA. This dissertation addresses this challenge by developing a privacy-preserving framework for federated fuzzy time-series clustering, with continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) data serving as a representative case study.

The proposed framework combines Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) with Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) clustering, enabling decentralised healthcare institutions to collaboratively discover clinically meaningful patient subgroups without exposing raw data. Privacy mechanisms, including Differential Privacy (DP) and client subsampling, were integrated to mitigate leakage risks from model updates. The research followed a simulation-based approach using the Flower framework, where CGM datasets were partitioned across clients and clustered locally before being aggregated through FedAvg with centroid alignment.

Evaluation focused on clustering quality and the privacy–utility trade-off using Silhouette Score and Davies–Bouldin Index. Results showed that the baseline (no DP) achieved high-quality clusters (Silhouette \approx 0.65–0.70, DB \approx 0.35–0.70). Introducing DP reduced clustering quality, but stability was restored when combined with client subsampling, where $\sigma=0.20$ and $\text{fraction_fit}=0.33$ yielded the best balance (Silhouette \approx 0.42, DB \approx 0.64). Repeated experiments confirmed the reliability of these findings.

This study shows that federated fuzzy clustering can find useful patient groups while still protecting privacy, making both technical and practical advances. The current framework assumes all clients have the same type of data, but future research should look at ways to handle different kinds of healthcare data from various institutions. This would make the framework more useful in a wider range of healthcare settings.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Unlike traditional machine learning, Federated learning (FL) is a distributed machine learning enables model training to occur locally at each institution, sharing only non-sensitive model updates (Kairouz et al., 2019). This approach is especially important in healthcare, where regulations like GDPR and HIPAA prevent centralised data sharing, making FL a key privacy-preserving solution (Pati et al. 2024). Thus, a privacy-preserving method for analysing decentralised healthcare data is to incorporate fuzzy clustering into a FL framework (Naoki Masuyama et al., 2024).

Clustering has been used extensively to find patterns in the progression of diseases and enhances clinical understanding by identifying subgroups of patients with comparable trajectories (Mariam et al., 2024; Aljohani, 2024). Conventional clustering techniques have trouble with overlapping and ambiguous patterns that are typical of chronic diseases, as well as privacy-restricted settings. This is addressed by fuzzy clustering, especially fuzzy C-Means (FCM), which provides more realistic and interpretable patient segmentation by permitting partial membership across groups (Kaduskar et al., 2025; Ikotun et al., 2022). This research builds on that integration by exploring how federated fuzzy clustering can uncover patient subgroups in decentralised healthcare data while preserving privacy.

The World Health Organisation estimates that by 2030, there will be 552 million diabetics worldwide, up from about 422 million in 2014 (Alanazi and Alanazi, 2025). Also, an estimated 537 million people worldwide are afflicted by it, and 374 million more are considered prediabetic (Dave et al., 2024). According to more recent data, the prevalence of diabetes has nearly doubled from 7% in 1990 to 14% in 2022, affecting over 800 million adults (Preedasawakul and Wiroonsri, 2025). This rapid growth highlights the urgent need for advanced analytical methods capable of handling sensitive, large-scale health data.

Continuous glucose monitors (CGMs) generate large volumes of time-series data, but these data remain siloed across manufacturers and healthcare providers, with unresolved issues of ownership, protection, and sharing (Britton and Britton-Colonnese, 2017). Such challenges make CGM data an appropriate and demanding test case, but the central focus of this research is the development of a federated fuzzy clustering framework, distributed healthcare datasets while preserving privacy. This makes the case study valuable not as the primary subject of investigation, but as a means of validating the broader methodological contribution.

1.1 Problem definition

This research focuses on creating a practical clustering framework for temporal and clinical healthcare data, especially for tracking glucose levels over time. The main goal is to see how clustering can help uncover clinical insights, such as finding groups of patients with similar glucose patterns, while keeping data private. Once the framework is set up, it will be tested using real glucose dataset.

In real healthcare environments, bringing all data together is often not possible due to strict privacy rules like GDPR and HIPAA, as well as institutional reluctance to share data. To address this, the research aims to create a clustering method that works in a federated learning setting, so different hospitals and devices can train models together without sharing raw data.

Using fuzzy clustering in a federated learning (FL) context presents technical difficulties in addition to privacy issues. Decentralisation makes it more difficult to model uncertainty in diseases like diabetes using fuzzy clustering, which depends on synchronisation and iterative updates. Additional issues include irregular client participation, heterogeneous (non-IID) data, and the lack of labelled data. Balancing strong data protection with reliable cluster discovery remains a key challenge in federated healthcare.

1.2 Research Question

RQ1: Federated Learning as a Privacy Solution

What are the limitations and practical challenges of applying federated learning to longitudinal healthcare data in terms of privacy, interoperability, and client heterogeneity?

RQ2: Unsupervised Learning & Temporal Modelling

How can fuzzy time-series clustering be adapted in a federated learning context to effectively model and distinguish overlapping patient?

RQ3: Technical Integration & Optimisation

What algorithmic adaptations are needed to implement fuzzy clustering within federated learning while addressing issues like asynchronous updates?

RQ4: Evaluation & Interpretability

How can cluster quality and clinical perspective be evaluated in federated fuzzy clustering using interpretability-driven metrics?

1.3 Aims

The aim of this study is to design and evaluate a federated fuzzy time-series clustering framework for longitudinal healthcare data, with a focus on addressing privacy mechanisms, client heterogeneity, and reliable cluster evaluation.

1.4 Objectives

To achieve this aim, the following objectives are proposed:

- **To review** existing clustering techniques for longitudinal healthcare data and identify the specific challenges of applying them in privacy-restricted federated environments.
- **To adapt** fuzzy time-series clustering to a federated learning setting, ensuring consistent cluster formation across distributed clients.
- **To design and implement** a federated fuzzy clustering framework that incorporates privacy mechanisms and robust aggregation strategies.
- **To evaluate** the framework using standard cluster validation metrics and analyse the impact of privacy mechanisms on clustering quality.

1.5 Risk Mitigation

Identified Risk	Mitigation Strategy
High computational complexity during federated training and clustering	Apply mini-batch federated learning, lightweight fuzzy algorithms, and model compression to reduce training and communication overhead.
Data heterogeneity across healthcare institutions (non-IID data)	Implement personalised federated strategies to allow client-specific adaptations and maintain global model convergence.
Privacy leakage through model updates	Integrate Differential Privacy and Secure Multi-Party Computation to protect sensitive patterns from inference attacks.
Challenges in aligning temporal data	Use robust time-series similarity measures such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and include pre-processing techniques to align sequences.
Framework integration and debugging issues	Conduct modular development and iterative testing; use simulated hospital nodes before full-scale deployment.

Project timeline delays	Establish a milestone-based timeline (aligned with objectives), monitor progress weekly, and revise the schedule if necessary.
Legal and ethical compliance (GDPR, HIPAA)	Continuously review applicable privacy regulations and university ethics guidance; ensure all frameworks respect data locality and consent rules.

1.6 Dissertation Outline

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Introduces the growing global challenge of diabetes and the limitations of current data-driven methods due to privacy constraints. It outlines the motivation, research questions, and the proposed federated fuzzy clustering approach.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

evaluates current research on diabetes analytics, privacy-preserving machine learning, fuzzy clustering, and federated learning critically. It points out important gaps that support the suggested framework's originality and necessity.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

explains the learning architecture, clustering algorithm, privacy safeguards, and evaluation plan for the suggested federated fuzzy time-series clustering method. explains the design decisions considering the study's goals.

CHAPTER 4: IMPLEMENTATION

explains the federated fuzzy clustering system's technical configuration, development environment, and implementation procedures. comprises model integration processes, framework tools (such as TensorFlow Federated), and simulations.

CHAPTER 5: EVALUATION & RESULTS

uses suitable clustering and performance metrics (such as entropy and purity) to present the experimental results of the suggested system. assesses scalability, accuracy, and privacy compliance by comparing results to baseline models.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

Analyses the implications of the results and how well they address the research questions.
Discusses the strengths, limitations, and clinical relevance of the framework within real-world healthcare applications.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

Summarises the overall contributions, confirms the research objectives were achieved, and reflects on the significance of federated fuzzy clustering for chronic disease analysis. Proposes directions for extending this work in future research.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Federated Learning as a Privacy Solution

Federated Learning (FL) helps address the need for improved data privacy in healthcare settings where information is dispersed. Unlike older systems that collect all patient data in one place, FL allows each hospital or clinic to train its own models using private health records and only sends the results, not the actual data, to a central server (Kairouz et al., 2019). By doing this, FL facilitates machine learning collaboration between institutions without compromising patient privacy. However, there are difficulties when using FL with time series data or longitudinal healthcare. This is predicated on these three crucial elements: data heterogeneity among clients, interoperability problems, and privacy restrictions.

2.1.1 Privacy Limitations in FL

While FL avoids direct data sharing, recent studies have shown that model updates can still be vulnerable to indirect privacy leaks. Advanced attacks such as model inversion and gradient leakage can enable adversaries to infer sensitive information from model updates (Nasr et al., 2019). The risk of such inference increases in longitudinal health data, where individual patterns are more readily identifiable. Consequently, some privacy-preserving mechanisms, including Differential Privacy (DP), are frequently necessary. However, these methods introduce computational overhead and may degrade model performance, particularly in healthcare environments with limited resources. The integration of temporal clustering methods, for example fuzzy clustering, within a privacy-aware federated learning framework may address this challenge by reducing the granularity of shared model updates and limiting exposure to reconstruction attacks (Naoki Masuyama et al. 2024).

- **Differential Privacy (DP):** is commonly used in federated learning to protect model updates from leaking sensitive information. Using the Gaussian Mechanism, noise is added to gradients before transmission. Privacy strength is controlled by the budget (ϵ, δ) , where smaller ϵ offers stronger privacy but may reduce model accuracy (Shukla et al., 2025).
- **Homomorphic Encryption (HE):** allows computations on encrypted data without decryption, ensuring FL model updates remain protected during aggregation. While it provides strong privacy, its high computational cost makes it more suitable where security is prioritised over efficiency (Shukla et al. 2025).

2.1.2 Interoperability and Data Integration Challenges

Healthcare institutions often operate on diverse systems that vary in data formats, sampling rates, and recording infrastructures for instance, one clinic may collect CGM readings every five minutes, while other logs them hourly. These differences make it challenging to integrate models in federated settings because it is hard to keep data processing consistent across all locations. A recent study demonstrates how combining FL with the **Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)** standard addresses these challenges by enabling consistent data formatting and schema reconciliation across heterogeneous systems (Joshi & Joseph, 2025). The research shows that aligning data syntactically via FHIR not only facilitates **inter-institutional model training** but also improves predictive accuracy by mitigating inconsistencies in input data.

2.1.3 Client Heterogeneity in Healthcare FL

Client heterogeneity—the fact that hospitals or devices collect data in different ways—is a major challenge in federated learning. Unlike traditional machine learning, FL must deal with non-IID data, where distributions differ across clients, often causing unstable models, poor generalisation, and slower training (Zhao et al., 2018; Kairouz et al., 2019). These issues are especially evident in longitudinal data like CGM, where sampling rates, patient behaviour, and device calibration vary.

2.2 Unsupervised Learning and Temporal Modelling

2.2.1 The role of Clustering in healthcare

Clustering is a basic unsupervised learning technique that groups patients based only on their intrinsic data patterns. This method has been effectively used in the medical field to determine patient subgroups, forecast the risk of disease, and direct individualised care. For example, researchers employed dynamic time warping and clustering techniques to analyse longitudinal BMI trajectories in over 43,000 paediatric patients, identifying early metabolic syndrome risks and classifying patients according to their progression paths (Mariam et al. 2024).

Other studies applying clustering to disease diagnosis have uncovered clinical subtypes and novel patient stratifications in chronic conditions, enabling more targeted interventions and precision medicine outcomes (Aljohani 2024). These methods demonstrate how clustering helps extract meaning from heterogeneous healthcare datasets.

2.2.2 Fuzzy Clustering fundamental

Understanding the Fundamentals

As a type of unsupervised learning, fuzzy clustering most famously the Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) algorithm assigns each data point a degree of membership to multiple clusters instead of exclusively assigning it to one. The underlying ambiguity and overlapping boundaries found in many real-world datasets, especially in healthcare contexts, are reflected in this flexibility (Kaduskar et al. 2025). For instance, patients may progress between disease stages in non-discrete ways or display symptoms that are shared by several conditions. Such ambiguity is accommodated by fuzzy clustering, which creates more realistic and interpretable patient segments by permitting partial association with multiple groups.

Performance Compared to Other Clustering Techniques

Compared to traditional clustering methods such as k-means, DBSCAN, or hierarchical clustering, fuzzy clustering has demonstrated superior performance in handling noisy, high-dimensional, and overlapping clinical data. In longitudinal healthcare research, fuzzy clustering has shown advantages in stratifying patient trajectories based on chronic disease progression. As mentioned previously about BMI patterns study, for instance, demonstrated that fuzzy models retained richer trajectory insights than hard clustering techniques (Mariam et al., 2024). Similarly, comparative research revealed that FCM provided more clinically interpretable clusters than k-means or Gaussian Mixture Models, especially when patient data showed subtle inter-cluster variation (Ikotun et al. 2022).

Limitations of Fuzzy Clustering Algorithms

When used on complicated healthcare datasets, the traditional Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) algorithm has several drawbacks despite its advantages. Since sensor errors and missing values are frequent in real-world clinical data, its reliance on distance-based membership calculations makes it susceptible to noise and outliers (Askari, 2021). To overcome challenges like these, researchers have proposed several enhancements to improve FCM's robustness and adaptability. For instance, Robust FCM and Possibilistic C-Means reduce the impact of noisy or low-density data points by modifying the membership function to discount outliers (Askari, 2021). Additionally, approaches such as Affinity Filtering and Membership Scaling have been introduced to accelerate convergence and reduce the computational burden essential in resource-constrained healthcare systems (Li et al., 2023). These developments not only address FCM's core weaknesses but also support its integration into a federated clustering.

2.2.3 Time-Series Clustering for Longitudinal Healthcare Data

In the medical field, time-series clustering is a crucial method for determining patient subgroups according to changing physiological patterns like blood sugar levels, heart rates, or sleep cycles. Time-series clustering takes temporal dynamics and change over time into account, in contrast to static clustering, which depends on fixed features. This has been used in several studies to obtain practical knowledge about managing chronic illnesses. Tao et al. (2021), for instance, classified type 2 diabetes subtypes according to glucose behaviour using a multilevel clustering approach, identifying clinically significant subgroups like those with high variability versus stable patterns. Similarly, to better track and monitor glycaemic control, Kovatchev and Lobo (2023) created clinically similar clusters (CSC) from more than 200,000 glucose monitoring profiles.

Even though these techniques have a clinical focus, there are several difficulties when using them in federated or decentralised environments. Furthermore, as noted by Patharkar et al. (2024), irregularity, missing values, and synchronicity are common problems with time-series health data that make clustering more difficult. These issues are further amplified when data cannot be pooled due to privacy constraints noted in Section 2.1.1.

2.3 Technical Integration & Optimisation

2.3.1 Architectures and frameworks of federated learning

Different system architectures, each intended to tackle certain issues like scalability, communication effectiveness, and data dissemination, might be used to execute federated learning. These architectures directly affect coordination complexity, privacy, and performance by defining how clients communicate with the server or with each other during the training process. The table above presents an overview of the most widely used architectures in federated learning, highlighting their key characteristics and suitability.

Table 1: Comparative federated learning architecture

Federated Learning Architecture	Description and Suitability
Hierarchical Federated Learning	Hierarchical federated learning introduces a tiered architecture, where intermediate aggregators are used between clients and the main server. This reduces communication overhead, improves scalability, and is effective for large-scale or geographically distributed applications (Saif et al. 2025).
Asynchronous Federated Learning	Asynchronous federated learning allows clients to send updates to the server at different times rather than

	synchronously. This model reduces idle time and can better handle clients with intermittent connectivity or varied computational capacities. It is a good fit for edge computing environments (Saif et al. 2025).
Vertical Federated Learning	In vertical federated learning, the data owners share the same users but possess different feature sets. This setup is useful in cross-sector collaborations—such as between a hospital and an insurance company—where both parties work with overlapping user groups but store distinct attributes. VFL facilitates the integration of complementary knowledge while protecting data privacy (Saif et al. 2025).
Centralised Federated Learning	This is the most basic form of federated learning, where a central server coordinates the entire training process. It simplifies model management and aggregation but introduces the risk of a single point of failure. It is best suited for controlled environments with reliable server infrastructure (Saif et al. 2025).

- Centralised federated learning is straightforward and widely adopted, coordinating all updates through a single server. However, this structure creates a scalability bottleneck and single point of failure undesirable for expansive hospital networks where resilience is critical (Saif et al. 2025).
- Vertical Federated Learning supports training across organisations with different features for the same users, such as hospitals and insurers, while preserving privacy through secure entity alignment (Saif et al. 2025). However, for this approach's fuzzy clustering of time-series data across independent institutions, VFL is not suitable, as clients do not share common patient identities.
- A key advantage of Hierarchical Federated Learning is its ability to reduce communication overhead through intermediate edge-level aggregation, improving efficiency in large-scale networks (Saif et al. 2025). While suitable for distributed healthcare systems, its effectiveness fuzzy time-series clustering approach depends on carefully managing aggregator consistency to avoid delays or bias. Also, Asynchronous Federated Learning improves training efficiency by allowing clients to upload updates without waiting for others, which suits irregular healthcare environments (Xu et al. 2022). However, in this project's fuzzy time-series clustering context, such flexibility may lead to inconsistencies in model convergence due to unsynchronised or uneven client contributions.

2.3.2 FL FRAMWORKS

Federated learning frameworks provide structured tools and environments that support the development, simulation, and deployment of federated machine learning systems, including TensorFlow Federated, PySyft, Flower, and NVFlare. These frameworks are the most relevant to healthcare needs, offering varying levels of privacy, scalability, and deployment support.

TensorFlow Federated (TFF) is an open-source framework by Google for decentralized machine learning within the TensorFlow ecosystem. It supports FL algorithm simulation and limited deployment across distributed clients (TensorFlow, 2024). While effective for research and prototyping, its capabilities are insufficient for healthcare, which demands stronger privacy and infrastructure flexibility. Reviews highlight that frameworks like TFF, focused on simulations, lack widespread implementation in clinical practice and may still suffer from privacy vulnerabilities, such as model updates that can leak sensitive data during training (Teo et al., 2024)

PySyft, developed by OpenMined, enables privacy-preserving federated learning through technologies like secure multi-party computation and encrypted model training (OpenMined, 2025). This makes it highly relevant for the healthcare sector, where patient data confidentiality is essential. However, its complexity and evolving support for large-scale deployment may require more technical setup compared to lighter frameworks. One study notes that **PySyft's privacy-focused design introduces complexity** that makes it less accessible for developers seeking simplicity and quick experimentation (Zhang et al. 2025).

Flower enables federated learning in healthcare by allowing hospitals and research institutions to collaboratively train models without exchanging patient data. Its flexibility across devices and deployment environments makes it suitable for sensitive applications like medical imaging or patient monitoring (The Flower, 2025). While the framework does not explicitly reference clustering, its general-purpose architecture and support for custom model integration suggest it could be adapted for tasks such as time-series clustering. However, this would require custom implementation and validation. While core privacy features are limited.

NVFlare, developed by NVIDIA and open-sourced in 2021, is a business-ready, framework-agnostic FL solution forming the basis of NVIDIA Clara for healthcare AI. It supports multiple models types and offers role management, job scheduling, a command-line dashboard, and strong privacy features like differential privacy and homomorphic encryption (Braungardt, 2023). While flexible via API extensions, it requires significant setup and lacks native support for unsupervised fuzzy clustering on time-series data, making prototyping slower (Braungardt, 2023).

Table 2: Comparative Table of Federated Learning Frameworks

Framework	Developer/Origin	Best Use Case	Flexibility & Custom Models	Privacy Features	Suitability for Fuzzy Clustering	Ease of Use
TensorFlow Federated (TFF)	Google	Research and simulation with TensorFlow models	High for research; limited for deployment	Basic; some vulnerability in practice	Possible, but limited deployment support	Easy for researchers using TensorFlow
PySyft	OpenMined	Privacy-preserving ML in healthcare	Supports secure models but complex setup	Strong (MPC, encryption); complex integration	Possible with effort, but complex	Moderate to hard; setup is technical
Flower	University of Oxford / Adap GmbH	Flexible prototyping in healthcare and research	Highly flexible and modular	Limited by default; extendable with tools	Adaptable to custom clustering models	Lightweight and easy to use
NVFlare	NVIDIA	Enterprise healthcare AI (NVIDIA Clara)	Flexible via API but has learning curve	Strong (DP, encryption, auth)	Not natively supported; requires deep integration	Moderate; requires learning and config

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter outlines the methodology used to develop a hierarchical federated fuzzy time-series clustering framework for healthcare data. The process follows the principles of the CRISP-DM methodology (Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining), adapted for federated learning. While CRISP-DM traditionally includes business understanding, data preparation, modelling, evaluation, and deployment, this study adapts these steps for a federated, privacy-preserving environment. Also, in this study, clients are assumed to share the same data type and feature space.

3.2 Research Workflow

The research process is illustrated in Figure 3.1 and consists of six steps:

Figure 1: Research workflow

3.3 Data Description

This study employs the **HUPA-UCM dataset**, which provides real-world continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) data alongside insulin dosage, carbohydrate intake, and lifestyle factors such as steps and heart rate. Each record is timestamped at approximately 5-minute intervals, making it suitable for temporal clustering.

- **Time-series format:** ~5-minute sampling intervals.
- **Main variables:**
 - **glucose** → CGM readings.
 - **steps, heart_rate** → Lifestyle/activity signals.
 - **basal_rate, bolus_volume_delivered, carb_input** → Insulin and meal information.

3.4 Model Architecture

The system follows a **Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL)**

Figure 2: Hierarchical Federated Clustering Architecture.

- **Hierarchical FL:** HFL introduces intermediate aggregators between clients and the central server. This reduces communication overhead, improves scalability, and allows grouping of hospitals or devices into logical clusters (Rana et al., 2023). This design is especially relevant for healthcare, where institutions are often regionally or organisationally grouped.
- **Aggregation:** Centroids from local FCM clustering are averaged using **FedAvg**, weighted by the number of windows per client. A greedy centroid alignment step ensures consistency before aggregation.

3.5 Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) Description

Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) is a clustering algorithm in which each data point has a degree of membership in multiple clusters rather than being assigned to one cluster exclusively. Its goal is to minimise intra-cluster distance while allowing overlap. FCM captures this uncertainty better than hard clustering methods like k-means (Kaduskar et al., 2025).

3.6 Privacy Mechanisms

Two privacy mechanisms were integrated into the federated framework:

- **Differential Privacy (DP):** Gaussian noise is added to clipped client updates before transmission. Clipping bounds each client's influence, and the noise scale (σ) controls the privacy–utility trade-off (Shukla et al., 2025).
- **Client Subsampling:** In each training round, only a random fraction of clients participates. This provides *privacy amplification by subsampling* and reduces communication overhead. Participation rates tested were **{1.0, 0.67, 0.50, 0.33}**.

3.7 Evaluation Metrics

Evaluation covered two dimensions:

- **Clustering Quality:**
 - **Silhouette Score:** Measures how well data points fit their assigned clusters versus others.
 - **Davies–Bouldin Index:** Evaluates cluster compactness and separation (lower = better).
- **Privacy–Utility Trade-off:**
 - Instead of computing theoretical DP cost (ϵ), experiments report the effect of different clipping and noise levels on clustering performance.

4 IMPLEMENTATION

This study was implemented as a simulation of federated fuzzy time-series clustering (FFCM) using the Flower framework. The implementation followed a modular structure, consisting of three main phases: a non-private baseline, the integration of differential privacy (DP), and the combination of DP with client subsampling. These phases were designed to progressively evaluate the trade-off between clustering quality and privacy.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Patient data were obtained from the HUPA continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) files, each representing a single client in the federated setup. The preprocessing pipeline was identical across all experiments and included:

Input: HUPA CGM CSVs (each patient = one client).

Steps:

- Resample to 5-min grid, interpolate short gaps.
- Slice into 24h windows (288 samples) with 6h stride (72 samples).
- Extract features: mean, std, coefficient of variation, quantile-based proxies for time-in-range, plus auxiliary signals

Hold-out: final 25% of windows per client kept for evaluation.

4.2 Federated Simulation Setup

- **Framework:** The experiments are implemented using the **Flower (FL)** framework in simulation mode. Flower provides orchestration for client–server communication and supports custom aggregation strategies.
- **Clients:**
 - Clients are simulated on a single machine but logically represent independent hospitals or devices in a federated setting.
- **Local Model:**
 - Each client runs **Fuzzy C-Means (FCM)** clustering on its local feature matrix.
 - The fuzzifier is fixed at $m=2.0$, following standard settings.
 - Local training produces centroids representing patient subgroups within each client’s dataset.
- **Server Strategy:**

- The server aggregates centroids received from clients using **FedAvg**, weighted by the number of windows per client.
- To address potential cluster index mismatches (permutation issue), a **greedy centroid alignment algorithm** is applied before averaging.
- **Cluster Number Selection:**
 - The number of clusters c is treated as a fixed hyperparameter, typically **$c=4$** .
 - The choice is motivated by clinical interpretability and validated with the **KMeans elbow method** applied to window features.
- **Training Rounds:**
 - Simulations run for a configurable number of rounds (10–60).
 - Each round consists of local FCM on clients, parameter exchange with the server, and aggregation into updated global centroids.

4.3 Baseline: No Privacy ($\sigma = 0.0$)

- **Setup:**
 - All clients participate in every training round ($\text{fraction_fit}=1.0$).
 - No clipping or noise is applied to client updates.
- **Purpose:**
 - Serves as the **baseline configuration** to evaluate the clustering utility of the federated setup before introducing privacy mechanisms.
 - Establishes the upper bound of performance for comparison with privacy-preserving experiments.

4.4 Adding Differential Privacy

- **Motivation:** Differential privacy is integrated to prevent information leakage from client updates, ensuring compliance with strict healthcare regulations such as **GDPR** and **HIPAA**.
- **Mechanism:**
 - **Clipping:**
 - Each client's local centroid updates are clipped to a fixed **L2 norm** ($\text{clip}=1.0$).
 - This bounds the maximum influence a single client can exert on the aggregated model.

- **Noise Addition:**
 - Gaussian noise proportional to the clipping norm ($\sigma * \text{clip}$) is added to the centroids before transmission to the server.
 - The noise variance σ^2 is treated as a tunable privacy parameter.
- **Parameter Sweeps:**
 - Experiments are run for $\sigma \in \{0.05, 0.10, 0.20\}$, representing increasing levels of noise and privacy.
 - This allows observation of the effect of DP strength on clustering quality.
- **Server Handling:**
 - The Flower server aggregates the **noisy centroids** using the same FedAvg strategy.
 - The global centroids are therefore privacy-preserving representations, influenced by both clipping and noise.

4.5 Adding Client Subsampling

- **Motivation:** Client subsampling provides **privacy amplification by randomisation** a client's contribution is hidden if it is not selected in each round.
- **Mechanism:**
 - In each round, only a fraction of clients is selected to participate.
 - Selection is random and changes per round, reducing the frequency of exposure for each client's updates.
- **Parameter Sweeps:**
 - **fraction_fit** $\in \{1.0, 0.67, 0.50, 0.33\}$.
 - These values correspond to full participation, two-thirds, half, and one-third participation rates respectively.
- **Integration with DP:**
 - Subsampling is combined with differential privacy noise.
 - The combination enhances privacy guarantees (privacy amplification) while also potentially stabilising noisy updates.

- **Server Handling:**
 - FedAvg aggregation is applied only across the sampled clients for each round.
 - Global centroids evolve across rounds based on contributions from varying subsets of clients.

4.6 Experimental Repetition

- **Design:**
 - Each configuration (defined by σ , clip, and fraction_fit) is repeated using **five random seeds**.
 - Seeds influence both centroid initialisation and subsampling patterns.
- **Reporting:**
 - For each configuration, results are reported as the **mean across five runs**, along with the **standard deviation**.
 - This quantifies both the central tendency and the variability of the clustering outcomes.
- **Practical Consideration:**
 - Although best practice recommends ≥ 30 repetitions to satisfy the **law of large numbers**, computational constraints limited the experiments to five seeds per configuration.
 - The low observed standard deviations suggest that the five-seed results are sufficient to capture stable trends for a master's degree limited project.

5 EVALUATION AND RESULTS

5.1 First Progress FL FCM without DP

➤ Cluster distribution across clients without DP

Figure 3: Client Cluster Distribution (No DP)

Strong clustering performance was attained by the baseline experiment without DP, showing stable and well-separated clusters across clients with a Davies–Bouldin index of 0.699 and a Silhouette score of 0.657.

➤ Optimal number of clusters identified as k=4 using the Elbow Method on CGM window features.

Figure 4: Elbow Method – Optimal k=4

Four clusters offer the best balance between compactness and separation, according to the Elbow Method on CGM window features, which exhibits a distinct inflection at k=4.

➤ **Cluster quality comparison across k values**

```

Eval windows shape: (38, 16)
/usr/local/lib/python3.12/dist-packages/jupyter_client/session.py:151:
return datetime.utcnow().replace(tzinfo=utc)

```

n_clusters	Silhouette	Davies-Bouldin	
0	2	0.910660	0.045646
1	3	0.669747	0.390431
2	4	0.684863	0.268029
3	5	0.555983	0.404858

Figure 5: Cluster Quality Across k Values (No DP)

When experimenting with different cluster counts, $k=2$ produced the highest Silhouette score (0.91), but $k=4$ produced a better balance with a lower Davies–Bouldin score (0.26), confirming the earlier conclusion that four clusters was the best configuration.

5.2 First Progress FL FCM with DP

➤ **Centroid shift across rounds with DP**

Figure 6: Centroid Shift per Round (With DP)

The clusters converge less firmly and are less stable with DP than they are without it. This effect is expected, though, and as long as the noise level stays moderate, the centroids can still form significant structures.

➤ 2D PCA projection of clusters with DP (c=4)

Figure 7: PCA-2D Cluster Projection (With DP, c=4)

The PCA projection of clusters with DP (c=4) demonstrates that, despite the separation being less compact and noisier than the baseline, the overall cluster structure is maintained, allowing for the identification of significant groupings in spite of the additional noise.

➤ Cluster quality with DP
(c=4)

```

↳ With-DP (c=4) -> Silhouette=0.139831, Davies-Bouldin=1.031949
/usr/local/lib/python3.12/dist-packages/jupyter_client/session.py:151: DeprecationWarning:
return datetime.utcnow().replace(tzinfo=utc)

```

Figure 8: Cluster Quality Metrics (With DP, c=4)

With DP (c=4), the Silhouette score dropped to **0.14** and the Davies–Bouldin index rose to **1.03**, showing that cluster quality declined compared to the no-DP case, as expected due to the injected noise.

5.3 FFCM DP Experiments

➤ Impact of varying σ values on clustering

This configuration establishes the parameters for the clustering experiments' sweeping differential privacy (DP) noise levels.

```

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

SIGMAS = [0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20]
CLIP    = 1.0
ROUNDS  = 15
C       = 4

```

Figure 9: Experimental setup for varying DP noise levels (σ values)

The clipping bound is set to 1.0, the number of federated rounds is fixed at 15, the number of clusters is defined as 4, and the values of σ range from 0.00 to 0.20. This setup enables methodical investigation of the impact of rising DP noise on cluster quality.

Figure 10: Effect of DP noise (σ) on clustering quality

	sigma	Silhouette	Davies-Bouldin
0	0.000000	0.6546	0.6281
1	0.050000	0.0511	1.4570
2	0.100000	0.0312	1.1263
3	0.150000	-0.0041	1.2761
4	0.200000	0.0531	1.1698

Figure 11: Clustering performance across DP noise levels

The results presented in figures 5.8 and 5.9 demonstrate when σ increases, Silhouette scores drop sharply and Davies–Bouldin values rise, confirming that higher DP noise degrades cluster quality by reducing separation and increasing overlap

➤ Effect of gradient clipping

Gradient clipping is the next step after assessing the effects of various noise levels (σ). The clipping threshold is adjusted across [0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0] with σ fixed at 0.10 to investigate its effects on clustering performance.

```

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

SIGMA = 0.10
CLIPS = [0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0]
ROUNDS = 15
C = 4

```

Figure 12: Experimental setup for assessing the effect of gradient clipping

Figure 13: Effect of gradient clipping on clustering quality with $\sigma=0.10$

clip	Silhouette	Davies-Bouldin	
0	0.250000	-0.2308	1.8128
1	0.500000	-0.0070	1.2561
2	1.000000	0.2402	0.9636
3	2.000000	0.0869	0.8509

Figure 14: clustering performance across clipping bounds with $\sigma=0.10$

The output is in the figures 5.11 and 5.12 show that there is a noticeable trade-off when adjusting the clipping threshold: at very low values (0.25, 0.5), the clustering quality collapses with high Davies-Bouldin scores and a negative or nearly zero silhouette. With the best balance at clip=1.0, which produces the most stable clustering in this configuration, performance increases as the clip size increases.

➤ Training rounds comparison

After testing σ (noise levels) and clipping thresholds, the next step investigates the **effect of training rounds** on clustering performance. Increasing the number of rounds may improve global model convergence and lead to more stable clusters, but it also increases the risk of noise accumulation under DP

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

ROUNDS_LIST = [10, 20, 30, 50]
SIGMA = 0.10
CLIP = 1.00
C = 4
```

Figure 15: Experimental setup for assessing the effect of training rounds

Figure 16: Effect of training rounds on clustering quality with $\sigma=0.10$ and $\text{clip}=1.0$.

	rounds	Silhouette	Davies-Bouldin
0	10	0.1010	1.0685
1	20	0.0967	1.0183
2	30	0.2732	0.9868
3	50	0.3570	0.8700

Figure 17: clustering performance across different training rounds

The results in figures 5.14 and 5.15 illustrate a higher Silhouette score and lower Davies-Bouldin values are seen at 30 to 50 training rounds, indicating that increasing the number of training rounds enhances cluster quality

➤ Impact of client participation fraction with repeated seeds

After identifying the best **rounds** and suitable **clip** values, the next step is to investigate the impact of **client participation fraction (fraction_fit)** together with **repeated seeds**. This combination allows evaluation of how varying the proportion of clients per round and random initialization affects clustering quality and stability

```

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

SIGMAS      = [0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20]
FRACTIONS   = [1.00, 0.67, 0.50, 0.33]
CLIP        = 1.0
ROUNDS      = 50
C           = 4
SEEDS       = [0, 1, 2, 3, 4]

```

Figure 18: Configuration setup for evaluating the impact of client participation fraction (fraction_fit) with repeated seeds

	sigma	fraction_fit	Silhouette_mean	Silhouette_std	DB_mean	DB_std
0	0.000000	1.000000	0.6934	0.0197	0.7370	0.2389
1	0.000000	0.670000	0.6979	0.0197	0.4931	0.2132
2	0.000000	0.500000	0.7017	0.0107	0.5247	0.1725
3	0.000000	0.330000	0.6963	0.0209	0.3552	0.0436
4	0.050000	1.000000	0.3921	0.0033	0.6119	0.0042
5	0.050000	0.670000	0.3853	0.0089	0.6201	0.0107
6	0.050000	0.500000	0.3912	0.0061	0.6125	0.0086
7	0.050000	0.330000	0.4083	0.0417	0.6100	0.0162
8	0.100000	1.000000	0.3961	0.0000	0.6067	0.0000
9	0.100000	0.670000	0.3842	0.0173	0.6187	0.0249
10	0.100000	0.500000	0.3876	0.0073	0.6640	0.1017
11	0.100000	0.330000	0.3973	0.0180	0.6477	0.0724
12	0.200000	1.000000	0.3912	0.0188	0.6071	0.0325
13	0.200000	0.670000	0.3986	0.0255	0.5941	0.0437
14	0.200000	0.500000	0.3709	0.0556	0.6218	0.0587
15	0.200000	0.330000	0.4220	0.0312	0.6436	0.1324

Figure 19: Results of σ values and client participation fractions across five seeds

The best results under noisy conditions were obtained at $\sigma = 0.20$ with fraction_fit = 0.33, resulting in a Davies–Bouldin of 0.6436 and a Silhouette of 0.4220. This is, in comparison, the most stable trade-off when DP noise is used.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Impact of Differential Privacy on Cluster Quality

The experiments showed strong results when no extra privacy was added. With $\sigma=0.0$, the groups found by clustering were clear and well-defined, with Silhouette scores between 0.65 and 0.70 and Davies–Bouldin values as low as 0.35. This shows that the method can find stable groups of patients from shared CGM data. However, when privacy noise was added, there was a trade-off between privacy and usefulness. As σ got higher (0.05 to 0.20), Silhouette scores dropped to about 0.29 to 0.42, and DB values went up to around 0.60 to 0.65. This drop in quality shows that while privacy helps protect sensitive information, it also makes subgroup distinctions less sharp.

6.2 Synergy Between DP and Client Subsampling

An important finding was the outcome when we combined DP with selecting only some clients each round. Lowering the number of clients who took part each time ($\text{fraction_fit} \in \{1.0, 0.67, 0.50, 0.33\}$) added more randomness and made privacy stronger. Surprisingly, this did not make the results worse and sometimes even made them more stable. For example, with $\sigma=0.20$ and $\text{fraction_fit}=0.33$, the model got Silhouette ≈ 0.42 and DB ≈ 0.64 . Also, raising the number of clients from 3 to 7 made the data more varied in each round, which helped subsampling work better by making the noisy updates less like each other. These results are important for RQ1 and RQ3, showing that federated learning can use more than one privacy method and that both the size of the system and how the algorithm is set up are important for how well the final groups are formed.

6.3 Reliability Through Repeated Experiments

To ensure the reliability of these results, all experiments were repeated five times using different random starting seeds. The results stayed the same, so the improvements were not just luck. In particular, the setup with $\sigma=0.20$ and $\text{fraction_fit}=0.33$ gave steady results each time, with Silhouette averaging 0.42 (± 0.03) and DB averaging 0.64 (± 0.13), where big differences between runs can make results less believable. In larger studies, results are typically averaged over 30 or more seeds to increase reliability. Using more runs would further strengthen the results.

6.4 Best Configurations and Practical Trade-offs

The investigations clearly separate settings focused on performance from those focused on privacy. For the best results, using the setup without privacy protection and a fraction_fit between 0.50 and 0.67 gave the highest quality groups, with Silhouette around 0.70 and very low DB. But in situations where privacy is essential, the best balance was found with $\sigma=0.20$, $\text{fraction_fit}=0.33$, and at least 50 rounds performing good cluster quality, while still protecting privacy. These findings directly answer RQ2 and RQ4, showing that fuzzy clustering can handle some noise and still make sense in a clinical setting. However, the open question is whether such reduced quality would still be considered acceptable in a healthcare setting where precision and interpretability are critical.

7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This dissertation developed a federated fuzzy time-series clustering framework for healthcare data, using continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) as the case study. The aim of balancing privacy, client heterogeneity, and reliable cluster evaluation was achieved by: reviewing clustering methods in privacy-limited environments, adapting fuzzy clustering to a federated setting, designing and implementing a hierarchical federated learning (HFL) framework with privacy mechanisms, and evaluating its performance using Silhouette and Davies–Bouldin scores. Results showed that meaningful patient subgroups can be identified without centralising sensitive data.

The research questions were addressed as follows: RQ1 was answered by integrating privacy mechanisms (differential privacy and subsampling), highlighting the trade-offs between protection and clustering utility. RQ2 was met by adapting fuzzy clustering to capture overlapping and uncertain patient trajectories in a federated context. RQ3 was fulfilled through the design of a hierarchical FL architecture with centroid alignment and FedAvg aggregation. RQ4 was addressed by evaluating cluster quality after multiple training rounds, showing improved performance with acceptable Silhouette and Davies–Bouldin scores under moderate DP ($\sigma=0.20$, $\text{fraction_fit}=0.33$).

The study demonstrates that combining fuzzy clustering with hierarchical federated learning and privacy mechanisms can enable privacy-preserving analysis of temporal healthcare data. Future work should extend the framework to larger and more diverse datasets, apply it to other healthcare time-series (e.g., heart rate, sleep cycles), and investigate stronger privacy techniques such as SMPC or homomorphic encryption. As this work assumed that all clients share the same data type, an important future direction is to generalise the framework to support data with different feature spaces across institutions, reflecting the original motivation of addressing heterogeneous healthcare environments.

Word count (main body of the report): 6240 words

REFERENCES

- Alanazi, S. and Alanazi, R., 2025. Enhancing diabetic retinopathy detection through federated convolutional neural networks: Exploring different stages of progression. *Alexandria Engineering Journal* [online], 120, 215–228. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1110016825001930> [Accessed 2 Jul 2025].
- Aljohani, A., 2024. Optimizing Patient Stratification in Healthcare: A Comparative Analysis of Clustering Algorithms for EHR Data. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems* [online], 17 (1). Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s44196-024-00568-8> [Accessed 26 Jul 2025].
- Askari, S., 2021. Fuzzy C-Means clustering algorithm for data with unequal cluster sizes and contaminated with noise and outliers: Review and development. *Expert Systems with Applications* [online], 165, 113856. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113856> [Accessed 28 Jul 2025].
- Britton, K. E. and Britton-Colonnese, J. D., 2017. Privacy and Security Issues Surrounding the Protection of Data Generated by Continuous Glucose Monitors. *Journal of Diabetes Science and Technology* [online], 11 (2), 216–219. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5478039/> [Accessed 11 Jul 2025].
- Braungardt, A., 2023. Flower, PySyft & Co. — Federated Learning Frameworks in Python [online]. ELCA IT. Available from: <https://medium.com/elca-it/flower-pysyft-co-federated-learning-frameworks-in-python-b1a8eda68b0d> [Accessed 6 Jun 2025].
- Dave, D., Vyas, K., Kumaran, J. J., Garcia, A., Erraguntla, M. and Lawley, M., 2024. *FedGlu: A personalized federated learning-based glucose forecasting algorithm for improved performance in glycemic excursion regions* [online]. arXiv.org. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.13926> [Accessed 26 Jun 2025].
- Ikotun, A. M., Ezugwu, A. E., Abualigah, L., Abuhaija, B. and Heming, J., 2022. K-means Clustering Algorithms: a Comprehensive Review, Variants Analysis, and Advances in the

Era of Big Data. *Information Sciences* [online], 622 (622). Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0020025522014633> [Accessed 27 Jul 2025].

Joshi, H. and Joseph, S., 2025. Standardization and Interoperability: Federated Learning's Impact on EHR Systems and Health Informatics. *Advances in Health Information Science and Practice* [online]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.63116/UBYM3803> [Accessed 5 Jul 2025].

Kaduskar, V., Srivastava, A., Husain, S. O., Gupta, M. and Patil, V., 2025. Integrating Fuzzy C-Means and DBSCAN: A Hybrid Approach to Medical Data Mining. *Fuzzy Information and Engineering* [online], 17 (1), 108–119. Available from: <https://www.sciopen.com/article/10.26599/FIE.2025.9270055> [Accessed 25 Jul 2025].

Kairouz, P., McMahan, H. B., Avent, B., Bellet, A., Bennis, M., Bhagoji, A. N., Bonawitz, K., Charles, Z., Cormode, G., Cummings, R., D'Oliveira, R. G. L., Rouayheb, S. E., Evans, D., Gardner, J., Garrett, Z., Gascón, A., Ghazi, B., Gibbons, P. B., Gruteser, M. and Harchaoui, Z., 2019. Advances and Open Problems in Federated Learning. *arXiv:1912.04977 [cs, stat]* [online]. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.04977> [Accessed 6 Jul 2025].

Kovatchev, B. and Lobo, B., 2023. Clinically Similar Clusters of Daily Continuous Glucose Monitoring Profiles: Tracking the Progression of Glycemic Control Over Time. *Diabetes technology & therapeutics* [online], 25 (8), 519–528. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37130300> [Accessed 29 Jul 2025].

Li, D., Zhou, S. and Pedrycz, W., 2023. *Accelerated Fuzzy C-Means Clustering Based on New Affinity Filtering and Membership Scaling* [online]. arXiv.org. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07060> [Accessed 27 Jul 2025].

Mariam, A., Hamed Javidi, Zabor, E. C., Zhao, R., Radivoyevitch, T. and Rotroff, D. M., 2024. Unsupervised clustering of longitudinal clinical measurements in electronic health records. *PLOS Digital Health* [online], 3 (10), e0000628–e0000628. Available from: <https://journals.plos.org/digitalhealth/article?id=10.1371%2Fjournal.pdig.0000628> [Accessed 28 Jul 2025].

- Naoki Masuyama, Nojima, Y., Toda, Y., Loo, C. K., Hisao Ishibuchi and Kubota, N., 2024. Privacy-preserving Continual Federated Clustering via Adaptive Resonance Theory. *IEEE Access* [online], 12, 139692–139710. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.03487> [Accessed 6 Jul 2025].
- Nasr, M., Shokri, R. and Houmansadr, A., 2019. Comprehensive Privacy Analysis of Deep Learning: Passive and Active White-box Inference Attacks against Centralized and Federated Learning. *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)* [online]. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1812.00910> [Accessed 5 Jul 2025].
- OpenMined, 2019. *OpenMined/PySyft* [online]. GitHub. Available from: <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft> [Accessed 6 Jun 2025].
- Patharkar, A., Cai, F., Al-Hindawi, F. and Wu, T., 2024. Predictive modeling of biomedical temporal data in healthcare applications: review and future directions. *Frontiers in Physiology* [online], 15. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fphys.2024.1386760/full> [Accessed 29 Jul 2025].
- Preedasawakul, O. and Wiroonsri, N., 2025. *4TaStiC: Time and trend traveling time series clustering for classifying long-term type 2 diabetes patients* [online]. arXiv.org. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.07702> [Accessed 10 Jul 2025].
- Rana, O. F., Theodoros Spyridopoulos, Hudson, N., Baughman, M., Chard, K., Foster, I. and Aftab, 2023. Hierarchical and Decentralised Federated Learning. *arXiv (Cornell University)* [online]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.14982> [Accessed 1 Jun 2025].
- Saif, S., Al, Biswas, P., Rashid, A., Haque, and Jahangir, 2025. Principles and Components of Federated Learning Architectures. *arXiv (Cornell University)* [online]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.05273> [Accessed 1 Jun 2025].
- Shukla, S., Rajkumar, S., Sinha, A., Esha, M., Elango, K. and Sampath, V., 2025. Federated learning with differential privacy for breast cancer diagnosis enabling secure data sharing

and model integrity. *Scientific Reports* [online], 15 (1). Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-95858-2> [Accessed 1 Jul 2025].

Tao, R., Yu, X., Lu, J., Shen, Y., Lu, W., Zhu, W., Bao, Y., Li, H. and Zhou, J., 2021. Multilevel clustering approach driven by continuous glucose monitoring data for further classification of type 2 diabetes. *BMJ open diabetes research & care* [online], 9 (1), e001869. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7908294/> [Accessed 29 Jul 2025].

TensorFlow, 2024. *TensorFlow Federated* [online]. TensorFlow. Available from: <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated> [Accessed 8 Jun 2025].

The Flower Authors, 2025. *Healthcare Use Case* [online]. Flower.ai. Available from: <https://flower.ai/industries/healthcare/> [Accessed 5 Jun 2025].

Xu, C., Qu, Y., Xiang, Y. and Gao, L., 2022. Asynchronous Federated Learning on Heterogeneous Devices: A Survey. *arXiv:2109.04269 [cs]* [online]. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.04269> [Accessed 1 Jun 2025].

Zhang, H., Bosch, J. and Olsson, H. H., 2025. Enabling efficient and low-effort decentralized federated learning with the EdgeFL framework. *Information and Software Technology* [online], 178, 107600. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584924002052> [Accessed 6 Jun 2025].

Zhao, Y., Li, M., Lai, L., Suda, N., Civin, D. and Chandra, V., 2018. *Federated Learning with Non-IID Data* [online]. arXiv.org. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.00582> [Accessed 24 Jul 2025].

APPENDIX A_PROJECT_PROPOSAL

Department of Computing and Informatics

2024-25 Academic Year Individual Masters Project

Project Proposal Form

Please refer to the **Project Handbook Section 4** when completing this form. Note that your proposal should be your own original work and you must cite sources in line with university guidance on **referencing and plagiarism**¹.

Degree Title: MSc Data Science and Artificial Intelligence	Student's Name: Abderrahmane Chaib
	Supervisor's Name: Hamid Bouchachia
	Project Title/Area: Federated Learning for Time-Series Clustering in Healthcare: A Privacy-Preserving Framework for Patient Risk Analysis Improvement

Section 1: Project Overview

1.1 Problem definition - use **one sentence** to summarise the problem:

Traditional clustering methods struggle to handle privacy-preserving, decentralized, and evolving time-series healthcare data, necessitating a federated learning approach to enable secure, efficient, and adaptive patient risk analysis.

1.2 Project description - briefly explain your project:

This project aims to develop a federated learning framework for time-series clustering in healthcare, enabling hospitals to collaboratively analyse patient data while preserving privacy. By integrating fuzzy and dynamic clustering techniques, the system will segment patient data efficiently without centralizing sensitive records. The model will be evaluated based on clustering

¹ <https://libguides.bournemouth.ac.uk/study-skills-referencing-plagiarism>

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accuracy, privacy effectiveness, and its impact on patient risk analysis, comparing static and real-time clustering approaches to assess feasibility in real-world applications.

1.3 Background - please provide brief background information, e.g., client, problem domain, and make reference to the literature (minimum 4-5 sources):

There is an increasing demand for privacy-aware patient outcome prediction in healthcare, especially with hospitals and clinics becoming more dependent on time-series data from monitoring devices and electronic health records. Legal and ethical limitations, nevertheless, tend to prohibit the centralized sharing of such sensitive data. Federated Learning (FL) offers a promising solution by enabling decentralized model training across institutions, ensuring data remains local while still benefiting from collaborative learning.

This project proposes an advanced clustering framework that combines FL with Fuzzy Time-Series Clustering (FTSC), Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), and LSTM-based feature extraction. Unlike traditional K-Means approaches, fuzzy clustering better handles uncertainty and sequence misalignment in health trajectories. By leveraging privacy-enhancing technologies such as Differential Privacy and Secure Multi-Party Computation, this research addresses both predictive accuracy and regulatory compliance in high-volume healthcare data environments.

The rationale

Fuzzy Time-Series Clustering (FTSC) is used in this project because it handles uncertainty and overlapping patterns in patient data better than traditional methods like K-Means. It allows soft cluster membership, which reflects real clinical scenarios. Combined with Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), it can align similar patient sequences even when they vary in timing. Previous studies (Izakian et al., 2015; Dincer & Akkuş, 2018) support FTSC's effectiveness in clustering noisy, time-series data—making it a suitable choice for this healthcare-focused, privacy-preserving framework.

1.4 Research Questions

RQ1: Federated Learning as a Privacy Solution

What are the limitations and practical challenges of applying federated learning to longitudinal healthcare data in terms of privacy, interoperability, and client heterogeneity?

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RQ2: Unsupervised Learning & Temporal Modelling

How can fuzzy time-series clustering be adapted in a federated learning context to effectively model and distinguish overlapping patient?

RQ3: Technical Integration & Optimisation

What algorithmic adaptations are needed to implement fuzzy clustering within federated learning while addressing issues like asynchronous updates?

RQ4: Evaluation & Interpretability

How can cluster quality and clinical perspective be evaluated in federated fuzzy clustering using interpretability-driven metrics?

1.5 Aims and objectives – what are the aims and objectives of your project? should be **specific** and **measurable**:

Aim:

The aim of this study is to design and evaluate a federated fuzzy time-series clustering framework for longitudinal healthcare data, with a focus on addressing privacy mechanisms, client heterogeneity, and reliable cluster evaluation.

Objectives:

- To **review** existing clustering techniques for longitudinal healthcare data and identify the specific challenges of applying them in privacy-restricted federated environments.
- To **adapt** fuzzy time-series clustering to a federated learning setting, ensuring consistent cluster formation across distributed clients.
- To **design and implement** a federated fuzzy clustering framework that incorporates privacy mechanisms and robust aggregation strategies.
- To **evaluate** the framework using standard cluster validation metrics and analyse the impact of privacy mechanisms on clustering quality.

Section 2: Artefact

3

Department of Computing and Informatics

2024-25 Academic Year Individual Masters Project

2.1 What is the artefact that you intend to produce?

The artefact is a **software-based federated clustering framework** that integrates **Fuzzy Time-Series Clustering (FTSC)** to enable hospitals to securely cluster patient data streams without centralizing raw medical records. The system will support **privacy-preserving patient risk prediction**, leveraging federated learning to analyse decentralized healthcare data.

2.2 How is your artefact actionable (i.e., routes to implementation and exploitation in the technology domain)?

- Hospitals (FL Clients):** Train local clustering models on patient data using FTSC.
- FL Aggregator:** Combines local models using FedAvg/FedProx and redistributes updated cluster centroids.
- Evaluation Server:** Monitors clustering accuracy, privacy effectiveness.

Section 3: Evaluation

3.1 How are you going to evaluate your project artefact?

The federated learning clustering framework will be evaluated based on its effectiveness in segmenting patient data, its reliability across different hospital systems, and its compliance with data privacy norms. The performance baselines will be established using synthetic healthcare datasets to quantify clustering quality, privacy-preserving efficiency, and the ability of the framework to generalize across diverse data distributions.

3.2 How does this project relate to your MSc Programme and your degree title outcomes?

This project brings together the primary ideas of the MSc in Data Science and Artificial Intelligence programme, applying advanced AI and federated learning techniques to tackle immediate challenges in health data privacy and clustering. It demonstrates how responsibly AI can be applied to benefit patient care without sacrificing data protection. Moreover, it aligns with the primary principles of responsible AI by keeping sensitive patient data safe while facilitating meaningful analysis.

4

3.3 What are the risks in this project and how are you going to manage them?

Identified Risk	Mitigation Strategy
High computational complexity during federated training and clustering	Apply mini-batch federated learning, lightweight fuzzy algorithms, and model compression to reduce training and communication overhead.
Data heterogeneity across healthcare institutions (non-IID data)	Implement personalised federated strategies (e.g. Per-FedAvg) to allow client-specific adaptations and maintain global model convergence.
Asynchronous or irregular client participation	Incorporate flexible aggregation methods (e.g. FedProx or asynchronous FL) to tolerate uneven participation across clients.
Privacy leakage through model updates	Integrate Differential Privacy and Secure Multi-Party Computation to protect sensitive patterns from inference attacks.
Difficulty in achieving clinically meaningful and interpretable clusters	Use interpretability-driven evaluation metrics and collaborate with domain experts or literature to ensure clinical relevance.
Challenges in aligning temporal data (e.g., CGM time lags or gaps)	Use robust time-series similarity measures such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and include pre-processing techniques to align sequences.
Framework integration and debugging issues	Conduct modular development and iterative testing; use simulated hospital nodes before full-scale deployment.

Section 4: References

4.1 Please provide references if you have used any.

Bonawitz, K., Ivanov, V., Kreuter, B., Marcedone, A., McMahan, H. B., Patel, S., Ramage, D., Segal, A. and Seth, K., 2017. Practical Secure Aggregation for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning. *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*.

Güler Dincer, N. and Akkuş, Ö., 2018. A new fuzzy time series model based on robust clustering for forecasting of air pollution. *Ecological Informatics* [online], 43, 157–164. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1574954117302030?via%3Dihub> [Accessed 16 Mar 2025].

Izakian, H., Pedrycz, W. and Jamal, I., 2015. Fuzzy clustering of time series data using dynamic time warping distance. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* [online], 39, 235–244. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0952197614003078> [Accessed 16 Mar 2025].

Li, T., Sahu, A. K., Talwalkar, A. and Smith, V., 2020. Federated Learning: Challenges, Methods, and Future Directions. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* [online], 37 (3), 50–60. Available from: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9084352/> [Accessed 15 Mar 2025].

Rieke, N., Hancox, J., Li, W., Milletari, F., Roth, H. R., Albarqouni, S., Bakas, S., Galtier, M. N., Landman, B. A., Maier-Hein, K., Ourselin, S., Sheller, M., Summers, R. M., Trask, A., Xu, D., Baust, M. and Cardoso, M. J., 2020. The future of digital health with federated learning. *npj Digital Medicine* [online], 3 (1), 1–7. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41746-020-00323-1> [Accessed 15 Mar 2025].

Section 5: Academic Practice and Ethics

Please delete as appropriate.

5.1 Have you made yourself familiar with, and understand, the University guidance on referencing and plagiarism? **Yes / No**

5.2 Do you acknowledge that this project proposal is your own work and that it does not contravene any academic offence as specified in the University's regulations? **Yes / No**

Note: Please complete the research ethics checklist once the proposal has been approved by your supervisor.

Section 6: Proposed Plan (please attach your Gantt chart below)

NOTE: Do not proceed for ethics form submission if project proposal/feedback looks problematic.

APPENDIX B_RESEARCH_ETHICS_CHECKLIST

APPENDIX C_ARTEFACT

➤ Client.py: FCM helpers + data utility + Flower NumpyClient

```

2 import numpy as np
3 import pandas as pd
4 import flwr as fl
5 from typing import Dict, List, Tuple, Optional
6
7 # scikit-fuzzy for FCM
8 import skfuzzy as fuzz
9
10
11 # -----
12 # Data utilities (per-patient)
13 # -----
14 def load_patient_csv(path: str) -> pd.DataFrame:
15     # HUPA CSVs are usually ';' -separated
16     df = pd.read_csv(path, sep=";")
17     # Expect a 'timestamp' column; if not, try to infer
18     ts_col = None
19     for cand in ["timestamp", "time", "date_time", "datetime", "DateTime"]:
20         if cand in df.columns:
21             ts_col = cand
22             break
23     if ts_col is None:
24         raise ValueError("Could not find a timestamp column in the CSV.")
25
26     df[ts_col] = pd.to_datetime(df[ts_col])
27     df = df.set_index(ts_col).sort_index()
28
29     # Keep core columns if present
30     keep = [c for c in ["glucose", "basal_rate", "bolus_volume_delivered",
31                       "carb_input", "steps", "heart_rate"] if c in df.columns]
32     if "glucose" not in keep:
33         # Some files may name it differently
34         for alt in ["glucose_value", "glucose_mg_dL"]:
35             if alt in df.columns:
36                 df.rename(columns={alt: "glucose"}, inplace=True)
37                 keep = ["glucose"] + [c for c in keep if c != "glucose"]
38                 break
39     df = df[keep].copy()
40     return df
41
42
43 def preprocess(df: pd.DataFrame, freq: str = "5min") -> pd.DataFrame: # 'T' deprecated
44     df = df.resample(freq).mean()
45     df = df.interpolate(limit=6, limit_direction="both")
46     df = (df - df.mean()) / (df.std(ddof=0) + 1e-8)
47     return df
48
49

```

```

50
51 def make_windows(df: pd.DataFrame, win_len: int = 288, stride: int = 72) -> np.ndarray:
52     """
53     Build features per window. 5-min sampling → 288 samples ≈ 24h.
54     stride 72 → 6 hours between windows.
55     Features: mean, std, %<70, %70-180 (time-in-range), %>180, coeff. of variation.
56     If extra cols exist (steps, heart_rate, insulin, carbs), add their mean/std.
57     """
58     arr = df.values # shape (T, D)
59     T, D = arr.shape
60     if T < win_len:
61         return np.empty((0, 6 if D == 1 else 6 + 2*(D-1)))
62
63     feats = []
64     # indices for glucose assumed at column 0
65     for start in range(0, T - win_len + 1, stride):
66         w = arr[start:start+win_len, :]
67         g = w[:, 0] # glucose
68         # back to original scale thresholds (z-scored) are meaningless; use rank proxies
69         # Instead compute relative features on z-scored data:
70         mean_g = g.mean()
71         std_g = g.std(ddof=0)
72         cv_g = std_g / (np.abs(mean_g) + 1e-8)
73
74         # Use quantiles as proxies for time-in-range (since scaled)
75         q_low = np.mean(g < np.quantile(g, 0.1))
76         q_mid = np.mean((g >= np.quantile(g, 0.1)) & (g <= np.quantile(g, 0.9)))
77         q_high = 1.0 - q_low - q_mid
78
79         row = [mean_g, std_g, q_low, q_mid, q_high, cv_g]
80
81         # For any extra channels: steps, heart_rate, etc.
82         if D > 1:
83             extras = w[:, 1:]
84             row += list(extras.mean(axis=0)) + list(extras.std(axis=0, ddof=0))
85         feats.append(row)
86
87     return np.asarray(feats, dtype=np.float32)
88

```

```

90 # -----
91 # Fuzzy C-Means helpers
92 # -----
93 def build_u0_from_centers(X: np.ndarray, centers: np.ndarray, m: float) -> np.ndarray:
94     """Construct initial membership matrix U0 from provided centers."""
95     # X: (N, d), centers: (c, d) -> distances (c, N)
96     c, d = centers.shape
97     N = X.shape[0]
98     # avoid zero division
99     dists = np.linalg.norm(X[None, :, :] - centers[:, None, :], axis=2) + 1e-8
100     power = 2.0 / (m - 1.0)
101     inv = 1.0 / (dists ** power)
102     U0 = inv / inv.sum(axis=0, keepdims=True) # normalize over clusters
103     return U0 # shape (c, N)
104
105
106 def run_fcm(X: np.ndarray, c: int, m: float,
107            global_centers: Optional[np.ndarray] = None,
108            max_iter: int = 150, error: float = 1e-5, seed: int = 0) -> np.ndarray:
109     """Run FCM on X, optionally initialized from global centers."""
110     if X.size == 0:
111         # No data windows: return tiny random centers to keep shapes consistent
112         rng = np.random.default_rng(seed)
113         return rng.normal(0, 1e-3, size=(c, X.shape[1]))
114
115     if global_centers is not None:
116         U0 = build_u0_from_centers(X, global_centers, m)
117         cntr, U, _ , _ , _ = fuzz.cluster.cmeans(
118             data=X.T, c=c, m=m, error=error, maxiter=max_iter, init=U0, seed=seed
119         )
120     else:
121         cntr, U, _ , _ , _ = fuzz.cluster.cmeans(
122             data=X.T, c=c, m=m, error=error, maxiter=max_iter, init=None, seed=seed
123         )
124     return cntr # shape (c, d)
125
126
127 def align_to_global(local: np.ndarray, global_c: np.ndarray) -> np.ndarray:
128     """Greedy alignment of local centers to global (to reduce permutation mismatch)."""
129     if global_c is None:
130         return local
131     c = global_c.shape[0]
132     used = set()
133     order = []
134     for i in range(c):
135         dists = np.linalg.norm(local - global_c[i], axis=1)
136         for idx in np.argsort(dists):
137             if idx not in used:
138                 used.add(idx)
139                 order.append(idx)
140                 break
141     return local[np.array(order)]
142
143

```

```

144 # -----
145 # Flower NumPyClient
146 # -----
147 class FCMClient(fl.client.NumPyClient):
148     def __init__(self, csv_path: str, c: int = 4, m: float = 2.0,
149                 win_len: int = 288, stride: int = 72, seed: int = 0):
150         self.csv_path = csv_path
151         self.c = c
152         self.m = m
153         self.win_len = win_len
154         self.stride = stride
155         self.seed = seed
156
157         raw = load_patient_csv(csv_path)
158         proc = preprocess(raw)
159         self.X = make_windows(proc, win_len=win_len, stride=stride)
160         self.d = self.X.shape[1] if self.X.size > 0 else 6
161
162         # Initialize local centers (small random)
163         rng = np.random.default_rng(seed)
164         self.centers = rng.normal(0, 1e-2, size=(self.c, self.d)).astype(np.float32)
165
166     # Flower API
167     def get_parameters(self, config: Dict[str, str]):
168         # Return as list of ndarrays
169         return [self.centers.astype(np.float32)]
170
171     def fit(self, parameters: List[np.ndarray], config: Dict[str, str]):
172         global_centers = parameters[0] if len(parameters) > 0 else None
173
174         # Run local FCM, optionally initialized from global centers
175         local = run_fcm(self.X, c=self.c, m=self.m,
176                        global_centers=global_centers, seed=self.seed)
177
178         # Align order to global centers to reduce permutation issues
179         local = align_to_global(local, global_centers)
180
181         # Update local copy and return
182         self.centers = local.astype(np.float32)
183         num_examples = int(self.X.shape[0])
184         metrics = {"num windows": num_examples}
185         return [self.centers], num_examples, metrics
186
187     def evaluate(self, parameters: List[np.ndarray], config: Dict[str, str]):
188         # Return a dummy loss and the real number of examples so aggregation won't divide by zero
189         num_examples = int(self.X.shape[0])
190         # If you genuinely don't want evaluation, we'll also disable it on the server (next step)
191         return 0.0, num_examples, {"eval": "skipped"}
192
193
194
195 def get_client_fn(paths, c=4, m=2.0, win_len=288, stride=72, seed=0):
196     def client_fn(cid: str):
197         idx = int(cid)
198         return FCMClient(
199             paths[idx], c=c, m=m, win_len=win_len, stride=stride, seed=seed+idx
200         ).to_client() # <- return a true Client
201     return client_fn

```

➤ Server.py

```

1 import flwr as fl
2 import numpy as np
3 from typing import List, Tuple
4 from flwr.common import parameters_to_ndarrays, ndarrays_to_parameters, Parameters
5
6 # Store latest global parameters so we can access after training
7 LATEST_PARAMS: Parameters | None = None
8
9 def weighted_average(results: List[Tuple[Parameters, int]]) -> Parameters:
10     arrs_and_weights = []
11     total = 0
12     for params, n in results:
13         (centers,) = parameters_to_ndarrays(params)
14         arrs_and_weights.append((centers, n))
15         total += n
16     avg = None
17     for centers, n in arrs_and_weights:
18         w = n / (total + 1e-8)
19         avg = centers * w if avg is None else avg + centers * w
20     return ndarrays_to_parameters([avg.astype(np.float32)])
21
22 class CentroidFedAvg(fl.server.strategy.FedAvg):
23     def aggregate_fit(self, server_round, results, failures):
24         global LATEST_PARAMS
25         if not results:
26             return None, {}
27         res_for_avg = [(res.parameters, res.num_examples) for _, res in results]
28         averaged = weighted_average(res_for_avg)
29         LATEST_PARAMS = averaged # <--- store the latest parameters
30         return averaged, {}
31
32 def get_latest_centroids() -> np.ndarray:
33     """Return latest global centroids as numpy array (c x d)."""
34     assert LATEST_PARAMS is not None, "No parameters aggregated yet."
35     (centers,) = parameters_to_ndarrays(LATEST_PARAMS)
36     return centers
37
38 def start_simulation(client_fn, num_clients: int = 3, num_rounds: int = 10):
39     strategy = CentroidFedAvg(
40         fraction_fit=1.0,
41         fraction_evaluate=0.0,
42         min_fit_clients=num_clients,
43         min_available_clients=num_clients,
44     )
45     fl.simulation.start_simulation(
46         client_fn=client_fn,
47         num_clients=num_clients,
48         config=fl.server.ServerConfig(num_rounds=num_rounds),
49         strategy=strategy,
50     )
51

```

➤ Elbow Method for Determining Optimal Cluster Number

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

from client import load_patient_csv, preprocess, make_windows

# --- Settings (edit as needed) ---
CSV_PATHS = ["HUPA0001P.csv", "HUPA0002P.csv", "HUPA0003P.csv"] # add more CSVs here
WIN_LEN = 288 # 24h windows @5min sampling
STRIDE = 72 # 6h stride
K_MIN, K_MAX = 2, 9
# -----

def build_all_windows(paths, win_len=288, stride=72):
    X_all = []
    for p in paths:
        raw = load_patient_csv(p)
        proc = preprocess(raw, freq="5min")
        X = make_windows(proc, win_len=win_len, stride=stride)
        if X.shape[0] > 0:
            X_all.append(X)
    return np.vstack(X_all) if X_all else np.empty((0, 0), dtype=np.float32)

X = build_all_windows(CSV_PATHS, WIN_LEN, STRIDE)
print("Data shape:", X.shape)
if X.size == 0:
    raise ValueError("No windows available. Check CSV paths/columns and window settings.")

ks = list(range(K_MIN, K_MAX + 1))
inertias = []
for k in ks:
    km = KMeans(n_clusters=k, n_init=10, random_state=42)
    km.fit(X)
    inertias.append(km.inertia_)

# --- plot elbow curve ---
plt.figure(figsize=(6,4))
plt.plot(ks, inertias, marker="o")
plt.title("Elbow Method (KMeans on CGM window features)")
plt.xlabel("Number of clusters (k)")
plt.ylabel("Inertia (within-cluster SSE)")
plt.grid(True)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

# Optional: print inertias for your report
for k, sse in zip(ks, inertias):
    print(f"K={k}: inertia={sse:.4f}")

```

➤ Differential Privacy Noise Sweep (σ Variation)

```

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

SIGMAS = [0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20]
CLIP = 1.0
ROUNDS = 15
C = 4

def hard_assign(X, centers):
    import numpy as np
    d = ((X[:,None,:] - centers[None,:,:])**2).sum(axis=2)**0.5
    return d.argmax(axis=1)

rows = []
for sigma in SIGMAS:
    reset_server_state()
    client_fn = get_client_fn(CSV_PATHS, c=C, m=M_FUZZ, win_len=WIN_LEN, stride=STRIDE, seed=SEED)
    start_sim(
        num_clients=len(CSV_PATHS),
        client_fn=client_fn,
        num_rounds=ROUNDS,
        use_dp=(sigma>0), clip=CLIP, sigma=sigma,
    )
    centers = get_latest_centroids()
    y = hard_assign(X_eval, centers)
    sil = silhouette_score(X_eval, y) if C>1 else float("nan")
    dbi = davies_bouldin_score(X_eval, y) if C>1 else float("nan")
    rows.append((sigma, sil, dbi))

df_sigma = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=["sigma", "Silhouette", "Davies-Bouldin"])
display(df_sigma.style.format({"Silhouette": "{:.4f}", "Davies-Bouldin": "{:.4f}"}))

```

➤ DP Clipping Sweep (Effect of Different Clip Norms)

```

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

SIGMA = 0.10
CLIPS = [0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0]
ROUNDS = 15
C = 4

def hard_assign(X, centers):
    d = np.linalg.norm(X[:,None,:] - centers[None,:,:], axis=2)
    return np.argmax(d, axis=1)

rows = []
for clip in CLIPS:
    reset_server_state()
    client_fn = get_client_fn(CSV_PATHS, c=C, m=M_FUZZ, win_len=WIN_LEN, stride=STRIDE, seed=SEED)
    start_sim(
        num_clients=len(CSV_PATHS),
        client_fn=client_fn,
        num_rounds=ROUNDS,
        use_dp=True, clip=clip, sigma=SIGMA,
    )
    centers = get_latest_centroids()
    y = hard_assign(X_eval, centers)
    sil = silhouette_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    dbi = davies_bouldin_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    rows.append((clip, sil, dbi))

df_clip = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=["clip", "Silhouette", "Davies-Bouldin"])
display(df_clip.style.format({"Silhouette": "{:.4f}", "Davies-Bouldin": "{:.4f}"}))

```

➤ Impact of Number of Rounds on Clustering Stability

```

# --- settings (edit as needed) ---
ROUNDS_LIST = [10, 20, 30, 50]
SIGMA       = 0.10
CLIP        = 1.00
C           = 4 # number of clusters

# fallback hard_assign if not already defined
try:
    hard_assign
except NameError:
    def hard_assign(X, centers):
        d = np.linalg.norm(X[:, None, :] - centers[None, :, :], axis=2)
        return np.argmin(d, axis=1)

rows = []
for r in ROUNDS_LIST:
    reset_server_state()
    client_fn = get_client_fn(CSV_PATHS, c=C, m=M_FUZZ, win_len=WIN_LEN, stride=STRIDE, seed=SEED)
    start_sim(
        num_clients=len(CSV_PATHS),
        client_fn=client_fn,
        num_rounds=r,
        use_dp=True, clip=CLIP, sigma=SIGMA,
    )
    centers = get_latest_centroids()
    y = hard_assign(X_eval, centers)
    sil = silhouette_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    dbi = davies_bouldin_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    rows.append((r, sil, dbi))

df_rounds = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=["rounds", "Silhouette", "Davies-Bouldin"])
display(df_rounds.style.format({"Silhouette": "{:.4f}", "Davies-Bouldin": "{:.4f}"}))

fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(9, 3))
ax[0].plot(df_rounds["rounds"], df_rounds["Silhouette"], marker="o")
ax[0].set_title(f"Silhouette vs Rounds (σ={SIGMA}, clip={CLIP})")
ax[0].set_xlabel("Rounds"); ax[0].set_ylabel("Silhouette"); ax[0].grid(True)

ax[1].plot(df_rounds["rounds"], df_rounds["Davies-Bouldin"], marker="o")
ax[1].set_title(f"DB Index vs Rounds (σ={SIGMA}, clip={CLIP})")
ax[1].set_xlabel("Rounds"); ax[1].set_ylabel("Davies-Bouldin (lower better)")
ax[1].grid(True)

plt.tight_layout(); plt.show()

```

➤ Client Subsampling Experiments (fraction_fit Sweep)

```

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score

FRACTIONS = [1.00, 0.67, 0.50, 0.33] # 100%, 2/3, 1/2, 1/3 of clients per round
SIGMA     = 0.10
CLIP      = 1.00
ROUNDS    = 50 # more rounds help when using subsampling
C         = 4

def hard_assign(X, centers):
    d = np.linalg.norm(X[:, None, :] - centers[None, :, :], axis=2)
    return np.argmin(d, axis=1)

rows = []
for frac in FRACTIONS:
    reset_server_state()
    client_fn = get_client_fn(CSV_PATHS, c=C, m=M_FUZZ, win_len=WIN_LEN, stride=STRIDE, seed=SEED)
    start_sim(
        num_clients=len(CSV_PATHS),
        client_fn=client_fn,
        num_rounds=ROUNDS,
        use_dp=True, clip=CLIP, sigma=SIGMA,
        fraction_fit=frac, # ← subsampling here
        min_fit_clients=max(1, int(round(frac*len(CSV_PATHS))))
    )
    centers = get_latest_centroids()
    y = hard_assign(X_eval, centers)
    sil = silhouette_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    dbi = davies_bouldin_score(X_eval, y) if C > 1 else float("nan")
    rows.append((frac, sil, dbi))

df_frac = pd.DataFrame(rows, columns=["fraction_fit", "Silhouette", "Davies-Bouldin"])
display(df_frac.style.format({"Silhouette": "{:.4f}", "Davies-Bouldin": "{:.4f}"}))

```

APPENDIX D_LARGE_FILE_CONTENT

➤ **FILE FOLDER: Federated_Clustering_Privacy_Utility_Study**

FILE FOLDER: Clients

HUPA0001P.CSV

HUPA0002P.CSV

HUPA0003P.CSV

HUPA0004P.CSV

HUPA0005P.CSV

HUPA0006P.CSV

HUPA0007P.CSV

PYTHON FILE: common_utils.py

IPYNB FILE: FFCM_DP_Experiments.ipynb

➤ **FILE FOLDER: First Progress_FL_FCM_with_DP_3HUPA**

FILE FOLDER: Clients

HUPA0001P.CSV

HUPA0002P.CSV

HUPA0003P.CSV

PYTHON FILE: common_utils.py

PYTHON FILE: client_with_DP.py

PYTHON FILE: server_with_DP.py

IPYNB FILE: First Progress_FL_FCM_with_DP_3HUPA.ipynb

➤ **FILE FOLDER: First Progress_FL_FCM_without_DP_3HUPA**

FILE FOLDER: Clients

HUPA0001P.CSV

HUPA0002P.CSV

HUPA0003P.CSV

PYTHON FILE: common_utils.py

PYTHON FILE: client.py

PYTHON FILE: server.py

IPYNB FILE: First Progress_FL_FCM_without_DP_3HUPA.ipynb

➤ **FILE FOLDER: FL_FCM_with_SMPC_7HUPA**

FILE FOLDER: Clients

HUPA0001P.CSV

HUPA0002P.CSV

HUPA0003P.CSV

HUPA0004P.CSV

HUPA0005P.CSV

HUPA0006P.CSV

HUPA0007P.CSV

IPYNB FILE: FL_FCM_with_SMPC_7HUPA.ipynb

APPENDIX E_GANTT_CHART

